

Selecting a Location for an HPC Data Centre

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Abstract

Choosing the location is an important strategic task when planning a new data centre, as it will impact virtually every step of the planning and realisation process as well as the future operation of the centre and extension possibilities. It is not uncommon in the data centre industry to spend significant effort and resources on finding and acquiring the optimal site for a new data centre. It is therefore unsurprising, that the industry has written widely about the factors that ought to be considered, when selecting a future location. However, within the community of HPC research centres requirements in a number of areas tend to vary from those of the traditional data centres.

Based on a survey of the PRACE community to which 10 sites responded this paper sets out to discuss where requirements and options in terms of the search for a new location for an HPC centre differ from those of a traditional data centre and briefly discusses the criteria that this community attributes the most importance to when selecting a site.

1. To build or to retrofit?

Whilst supercomputers could initially be accommodated within existing buildings, the current highly energy-dense machines are much more demanding of their environment in terms of power, cooling and load bearing.

When an existing infrastructure reaches its limits, the question of retrofitting the existing structure or building a new one must be considered. The survey showed that the main reasons for a centre to elect to retrofit an existing building are:

- The difficulty to obtain the budget required for a new build (often larger than for a retrofit);
- The time consuming processes for obtaining planning and construction permits;
- The cost and scarcity of available land to build on.

Given that most HPC research centres operate in the public domain and do not charge for their services, funding for the retrofit or new construction must often be sought from governmental sources. This may require substantial time as this funding is often allocated in multi-year cycles. Being part of the public domain often also implies that the centre will need to comply with stricter procurement procedures than private companies. This again will lengthen the time to solution.

Time and resources permitting, the main advantages cited for the building of a new centre were:

- Planning, operating and maintenance are easier and can be optimised;
- It is easier to integrate energy efficiency measures;
- The structure can be specifically built to the requirements of the centre, thus making it more cost and energy

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effective;

- There are no limitations given by an existing building such as low ceilings, limited weight loads, limitations to changes of the exterior shell.

2. The freedom to choose

Many HPC research centres are linked to an established research institution such as a university or research laboratory that preceded the advent of computing. Being publicly funded these centres normally also have strong ties to local or regional government that may support the centre financially or otherwise.

The survey found that these factors strongly influence the choice of location for the construction of a new data centre when the current centre is already located close to or within a campus or research centre. Political expectation that the centre will remain in the town or region, related funding streams and synergies with co-located institutions or a university campus in terms of power and cooling supply, security, dedicated fire brigade and the proximity of the R&D environment favour the selection of a site within the campus or very close by.

The survey also found that those centres, that are not located within or near a campus or research centre display more freedom in choosing a location for a new centre. Their choice is primarily driven by the availability of land and funding. Whilst there is an example of a centre locating their new site a substantial distance from their current one, this remains an exception. In general, HPC centres favour the proximity to an existing R&D environment over a number of other factors such as local climate, energy costs and the attributes of available land parcels. In some cases, territory usage policy might also influence the choice.

3. Criteria considered when selecting a new site

When selecting a location for a new site, the survey shows that the main criteria considered are the following:

- Size, price and geological quality of the land
- Availability of reliable power supply and communication network
- Implied running costs (electricity, water, network access..)
- Amount of available power and possibility to increase this
- Availability of space for future extensions of the data centre
- Possibilities for use of free-cooling
- Easy access for deliveries and visitors

For the purposes of building a data centre, land parcels of regular shape and sufficient size, level and sound terrain are preferable, as they will offer the most freedom in planning and implementing the future structure. Strange shapes or disconnected land parcels may severely impact your ability to plan a structure to fit your operational requirements, whilst geological issues or strong inclines within the land parcel will have a strong implication in terms of the construction cost. A geological survey of the considered land parcel is strongly advisable in order to avoid expensive surprises.

The availability of a reliable power supply and communication network is critical to a data centre project. Bringing new power and communication lines to a site will be cost intensive and may require construction permits beyond your land parcel if the work will affect public roads or other land parcels.

Local prices for electricity, water and high bandwidth network access are also to be considered as they might impact the future running costs of the computing centre. These prices are not necessarily homogeneous throughout a country. Opportunities to reuse hot water produced by the cooling system should be considered.

Not only is it important to ascertain that a power supply is available, but also to know how large it is and whether it can be increased should this be required in the future. It is well worth discussing this up front with your energy supplier, who will also be able to give you indications of the quality of the power supplied. The latter will affect how you plan your UPS requirements.

Given that obtaining funding in the public sectors requires substantial time, advance planning of future needs is advisable in order to be able to accommodate future expansion needs in the same location without requiring the construction of a new centre. Underestimating future requirements may severely reduce the useful lifetime of the data centre.

Driven by the cost of energy and the political awareness of energy consumption, most data centres must consider free-cooling options as part of their steps towards ensuring energy and cost efficiency. It is important to consider all possible

sources of free-cooling as well as analysing the operability of their use in detail before planning commences. Whilst the use of free-cooling will substantially reduce operating costs, it will be necessary to make a study of the environmental impact as well as obtain all requisite permissions related to the use of such a source. Water and environmental protection regulations may impact their potential use substantially.

Access to the location should be easy for both future visitors and heavy transport vehicles. Not being able to drive up to the site with a standard delivery truck will make the installation of future HPC systems cumbersome and expensive.

Contrary to the conventional data centre industry, HPC centres attribute less importance to potential risk factors of a new location. This is largely due to the fact that they are situated within university or research campuses that have existed for a substantial number of years and risk factors are hence often low, well known and controlled. This type of situation also brings with it the added advantage of centralized access control and security surveillance. As the survey covers HPC centres located in Europe, most sites report, that they are not subject to particular natural hazards. Strong winds, electrical storms and ice rain are the main hazards cited. At the time of writing, political climate was not considered to be a potential risk factor in any of the partner countries.

4. Hurdles encountered and their effects

The main difficulties encountered by the sites surveyed relate to the political process to ensure funding, the attributes of available land parcel or existing building, environmental issues, limitations due to building, fire and security codes.

Convincing funding bodies of the centres requirements in terms of future growth (power, cooling, space) is often arduous and lengthy. Given the nature of HPC, it is very difficult, even for those in the business, to foresee changes in requirements more than one technology generation cycle into the future. This leads to a discrepancy between the expected lifetime for a building and the foreseeable hardware developments. Extrapolating on past developments is the only way of reaching conclusions about future requirements. Given that technology development is not linear and may drastically change as it did with the advent of CMOS technology, this method is at best imperfect.

Supercomputers are both power hungry and have high demands of their environment, making both the construction of the housing but also the future operation expensive. Putting forward requests for such large funding and getting them accepted requires time and a very well prepared argumentation of the requirements.

Finding space within an existing university or research campus may mean that the project has to deal with odd shaped or detached land parcels and the proximity of other buildings. This will make it challenging to plan a structure that can fully satisfy the operational requirements of the data centre and will most likely lead to a number of trade-offs. It is therefore critically necessary to consider up front, which trade-offs may arise and how the project can or cannot accommodate them. There will certainly be a number of criteria that cannot be negotiated without seriously hampering or endangering the success of the project. It is crucial to identify these at the outset in order to avoid making the wrong sacrifices.

The experience of the surveyed partners shows, that even when you find a good parcel of land, it is important to ensure that your construction plans fit within the local building, fire and security codes. Checking this in advance and working with a planning team that is fully apprised of the local rules and regulations will avoid the cost of modifications on the plans and related imperfections in the final result.

Checking out any possible environmental limitations is of utmost importance. Instances of local fauna and flora hampering, delaying or making construction plans impossible are not isolated and may cause severe increases in project cost and delays.

5. Recommendations - Important criteria for selecting a new location for an HPC centre

Overall, the accumulated experience of PRACE sites shows, that the most important criteria for selecting a new location for an HPC data centre are the following:

- Size, shape and geological quality of the land
- Availability of sufficient and extendable power supply
- Availability of good communication network
- Local prices for electricity, water and network access
- Availability of sufficient space for future extensions of the data centre
- Possibilities for use of free-cooling and / or reuse of hot water
- Proximity of R&D environment

- Easy access for deliveries and visitors
- Limitations due to local building, fire and security codes
- Limitations due to the protection of local fauna, flora, water etc.

6. Conclusion

The survey has clearly shown, that the public domain nature of the HPC research centres has a substantial impact on the selection process for a new location. Although existing literature about traditional data centres is undoubtedly useful in assisting the choice, it will not be entirely applicable or relevant for HPC data centres. Furthermore, a number of criteria, such as political and institutional ties, must be considered in the HPC centre evaluation process. Until recently, the HPC centres had no specific forum in which to discuss and exchange on their specific requirements as do the stakeholders of traditional data centres. The creation, within the PRACE project, of the annually held HPC Infrastructure Workshop seeks to provide such a forum. The respondents of the survey cited this workshop along with visits of other newly constructed HPC data centres as important factors in helping them determine requirements and identify and understand potential issues and solutions.

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